

Ethical Principles for OSCAR Well-being Mentoring Program (code of conduct)

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Responsibility

Both mentors and mentees will be aware that their behavior and actions might potentially impact the mentoring relationship and seek to take responsibility for those actions. Both mentors and mentees will be aware of potential areas for discrimination and bias and seek to act respectfully and inclusively with mentees.

Integrity

Mentors will reflect consciously on their domains of expertise, understanding their own levels of experience and competence, and shall offer their mentoring activities solely on those areas.

Excellence practice

Mentors shall develop their mentoring abilities and their expertise by systematically analyzing the feedback from mentees and by participating in relevant training provided by OSCAR.

Privacy and confidentiality

Both mentors and mentees must maintain the confidentiality of all the information shared during the mentoring interaction and be aware of the exceptions to privacy (e.g., illegal activity, danger to self or others). Both mentors and mentees shall be informed about types of events and situations where privacy and confidentiality can be breached.

Conflict of interest

Mentors will disclose any conflict of interest openly and transparently with the mentee and manage the conflict effectively, or agree to terminate the mentoring relationship when the conflict is not solvable. Mentors must not use the mentoring relationship or any information shared by the mentee in order to gain inappropriate financial or nonfinancial advantage.

Mentoring boundaries and roles

Mentors are responsible for establishing and managing clear and adequate roles and boundaries, preventing personal bias to influence the mentoring relationship. Mentees shall respect mentors and their beliefs and values and if necessary disclose information regarding any incongruence which may affect the mentoring process.

Ending professional relationships and on-going responsibilities

Mentors are aware that the privacy and confidentiality responsibilities continue even after the end of the mentoring relationship. Mentors will suggest and encourage mentees to stop the mentoring relationship if they believe it would be more helpful for them to seek other types of professional help (e.g., psychotherapy).

Contracting

Mentors and mentees will agree on their expectations regarding the mentoring, clarifying what they want to achieve with the relationship (goals), the length and frequency of sessions, and the methods of contact. Defined goals shall be revisited by both parts in order to assess the quality of the mentoring relationship.

Acceptance and revision of this code

This code is implemented once the platform is available for mentors and mentees. The use of the platform developed by OSCAR implicates the acceptance of this code. The code shall be reviewed every two years or whenever the management team of OSCAR finds it necessary.

***Disclaimer:** These principles are for orientation and reference in mentoring relationships. It does not constitute legal advice. Further guidance may be found in the [European Mentoring & Coaching Council's Code of Ethics](#)*